

Psychosocial perceptions on HIV cases in Bacoor City: Basis for HIV intervention programs

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Abstract

This paper is concerned with the psychosocial perceptions on Human Immunodeficiency Virus (HIV) and its correlation with five components that contribute to the increase of positive cases in Bacoor City, Cavite. The five components are as follows: Poverty, Teenage Promiscuity, Substance Abuse, Family Relationship, and Unsafe Sex. This study made use of descriptive research for identifying the characteristics of the phenomenon being studied. A self-made, four-point Likert Scale questionnaire created by the researchers to gain accurate results was also sent and validated by different individuals across various professions concerned with the medical and behavioral aspects of the study. The researchers utilized Google Forms to disseminate the questionnaires to random participants who agreed to participate in the data gathering portion of the study. All responses were then assessed by the research group's statistician. The results showed an average score for Poverty, Teenage Promiscuity, Substance Abuse, Family Relationship, and Unsafe Sex relative to HIV cases. Hence, there is no significant relationship between psychosocial perceptions and the five components presented. Different campaign programs advocated in relation to the five components were subsequently formulated by the researchers which might prove beneficial to the residents of Bacoor City, Cavite.

Keywords: *Human Immunodeficiency Virus (HIV), poverty, teenage promiscuity, substance abuse, family relationship, unsafe sex.*

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Introduction

The Philippines is among the countries with the fastest growing epidemic of Human Immunodeficiency Virus and Acquired Immunodeficiency Syndrome (HIV/AIDS) in Asia, with an estimated 4,300 cases in 2010 and rising to almost 10,500 in 2016. The Joint United Nations Program on HIV and AIDS (UNAIDS) stated that it had recorded about 13,384 new HIV cases, making the Philippines to belong in the eight countries contributing to the 85% increase of new HIV infections (UNAIDS, 2018). Given these figures, however, Dr. Louie Ocampo, UNAIDS Philippine country director, assured the public that although there was a huge increase of the new infections, the country still has a very low absolute number of HIV cases compared to African countries.

In a UNAIDS report from 2018, there were an approximate 77,000 individuals who are currently living with HIV, although 62,029 of those cases are diagnosed and reported.

Nevertheless, there have been slightly trivial possibilities in the Philippines to lessen the acquisition of HIV and impede a major epidemic from materializing. The UNAIDS accentuated the importance of creating HIV interventions that could produce up-to-date data and harnessing those to construct improved ones. Without those enhancements, HIV infection cases may reach about 201,000 in just eight years. Eamonn Murphy, Director of UNAIDS Regional Support Team for Asia-Pacific, said that if HIV intervention programs are redirected to mainly focus on the individuals who are much more at risk and where they are situated, the country could go back to a secured and steady condition and even terminate the HIV/AIDS outbreak as a danger to public health in the Philippines by 2030.

Despite the Philippines somewhat containing the outbreak among females who work for sex in 2007, the nation observed that new cases are notably coming from males having sex with males (MSM's) and transgender women having sex with males (TGW's). Data from 2016 showed that eighty-three (83) percent of just reported and verified HIV cases transpire in MSM's and TGW's- the majority of which came from the ages 15 to 24. Proper information on HIV transmission and prevention is essential to the discontinuation of the virus, as well as behavioral change among individuals that are at risk for infection. Yet, according to 2015 data from UNAIDS, only thirty-five (35) percent of those 15 to 24 years of age MSM's and TGW's were familiar with HIV preclusions. Condom used between MSM and TGW rose from 36% to 50% in four years, and that is significantly 80 percent below the target. Individuals who knew what their HIV status is by being tested rose from five percent (5%) in 2011 to only sixteen (16) percent in 2015. This is quite low considering that HIV testing is an essential attempt to access antiretroviral drugs that can save an HIV positive individual's life. Without the cooperation of these individuals, HIV cases will only continue to increase even if different intervention programs are laid out. In Bacoor, 726 cases of HIV/AIDS have been registered since 1984 until April of 2019. It is the highest accumulated number of occurrences in Cavite, together with the entire CALABARZON.

According to Dr. Michael Angelo Marquez, the Head of the Social Hygiene Clinic in Bacoor City, all new confirmed cases for April 2019 came from the 15 to 24 age group. In line with that information, he has been engaged in seminars in several schools of the city to raise awareness and prevent the spread of the virus. His team has been looking at young individuals, with ages ranging from 12 to 24 years old, as the focus for their educational awareness platforms about HIV transmission and prevention. In his words, *"We need to train them, increase their knowledge and encourage behavior change for them to become an effective messenger among their peers to prevent HIV and other sexually transmitted infections (STIs) in schools and the community."* The main objective is to educate the youth, hear their concerns on age-appropriate issues especially about adolescent reproductive health, and come up with wellness programs for better productivity. Peer education training programs are the most effective ways for risk reduction because the youth relies on trust and confidence amongst their peers, involving sensitive subject concerns such as reproductive health and curiosity.

The upsurge of new HIV cases prompted Philippine Health Secretary Francisco Duque III to finally implement Republic Act 11166 or the Philippine HIV and AIDS Policy Act, which has repealed the old HIV Law (RA 8504). The new law, which was approved on December 20th, 2018, enables easier access to learning about an individual's status as to whether he or she has tested positive. This is especially particular for young individuals aged 15 years old and above who may now undergo testing without parental or guardian consent. Since then, about 62 percent of new

HIV infections came from the youth, as this is critically claimed progress because suspected individuals can now undergo testing without discrimination. HIV testing is now also a routine procedure for prenatal care to avert transmission of the infection via mother to infant during pregnancy, labor, and breastfeeding. Refusal of health, accident, and life insurance coverage to people living with HIV (PLHIV) is now against the law. Republic Act No. 11166 has paved the way for instantaneous acceleration access to free treatment. PhilHealth has been asked to create and develop a revised benefits package which includes medication, treatment, and diagnostics for both in-patients and out-patients. The confidentiality clause has also been updated and provides absolute protection to PLHIV against unlawful access to their medical information. Furthermore, section 49 in this new Republic Act has been enhanced and modernized to address the discrimination issues faced by PLHIV's in the workplace, learning institutions, travel and habitation, shelter, exclusion from being offered credit and insurance services, hospitals and health establishments, denial of burial services and abuse. This new legislation comes safety and protection for all PLHIV and could be the way to stop a major health problem from spreading further.

Cases of HIV/Aids in a certain area and the continuous spread of this is a serious matter. According to HIV/Aids and Art Registry of the Philippines (HARP), Cavite has 11,504 reported cases of HIV as of March 2019. According to a statement of Dr. Michael Angelo Marquez, Bacoor City Health Officer medical office, on a training seminar for HIV/Aids of which he disclosed that Bacoor City has the highest case of HIV/Aids recorded in the region since 1984 to April 2019 with 726 cases, followed by Dasmariñas with 686 cases, and Imus City with 616 cases. He also stated that all new confirmed cases last April came from 15-24 age group.

Methods

Quantitative research is structured to expose the array of actions and beliefs of a target population that affects it regarding specific topics or issues. It is a form of research where the data that the respondents collected is then translated into a statistical result. The researchers used descriptive analysis to describe the characteristics of the phenomenon that is being studied, which is with the use of describing the demographic profile. In this type of research, the involvement of a large number of respondents is needed for comparison, the description, and interpretation of gathered data (QuestionPro, n.d.).

The researcher opted for a survey research method because it worked best to address the study's questions and purposes. The survey analysis is one that analyzes a group of individuals or items by gathering information from only a few individuals or items considered to stand for the entire community (Nworgu, 1991).

The researchers constructed a self-made survey form that will assess perceptions of non-HIV individuals towards HIV positive patients using the following factors: (a) poverty, (b) teenage promiscuity, (c) substance abuse, (d) family relationship, and (e) unsafe sex. The content of the research instrument underwent face and content validity. Researchers looked for subject matter experts who rated each item per factor whether it is rejected, revised, or removed. With the aid of statistics, the researchers identified items with correlation alpha at .80. The researchers used the

Likert Scale type to identify or specify the respondents' level of agreement or disagreement on a symmetric agree-disagree scale for a series of statements. The format of Likert Scale used in this study shows as follows: Strongly Disagree, Disagree, Agree and Strongly Agree. It is one of the most used approached in gathering data in a quantitative research. Due to the immediate national lockdown brought by the COVID-19 pandemic, questionnaires were submitted via google forms survey and were distributed to the target population and only completed questionnaires were analyzed.

The researchers underwent a title proposal. After a title was chosen and approved, a go signal from panel members was given to the researchers in drafting chapters one to three of the research paper. Library research was undertaken to enhance related literature and studies that were important in increasing research substance. The researchers constructed a self-made survey to measure and determine the psychosocial perceptions HIV positive individuals towards PLHIV. After items for each factor were formulated, the self-made survey underwent face and content validity. With the aid of subject matter experts, scores were collated and statistically ran to compute the reliability coefficient. Informed consent and confidentiality were indicated in the letter along with the valid test. Survey questionnaire forms were distributed at random, non-HIV citizens of Bacoor, Cavite. Once data was made available, it was collated and statistically ran in order to get results.

Results and Analysis

Table 1. Frequency Distribution per Demographic Profile (n=158)

Demographic Profile	Variable	Frequency	Percentage	Rank
Sex	Male	44	28	2
	Female	114	72	1
Age	33 and above	14	9	3.5
	28 to 32 years old	14	9	3.5
	23 to 27 years old	49	31	2
	18 to 22 years old	81	51	1
Highest Educational Attainment	College graduate	84	53	1
	College undergraduate	57	36	2
	High school graduate	17	11	3

The table reveals the frequency distribution of respondents. For sex, 44 out of 158 respondents are males with 28 percent, while 114 out of 158 respondents are females with 72 percent. Therefore, there are more female respondents who took part in the study. For age, 14 out of 158 respondents are 33 years old and above with 9 percent, 14 out of 158 respondents are 28 to 32 years old with 9 percent, 49 out of 158 respondents are 23 to 27 years old with 31 percent, while 81 out of 158 are 18 to 22 years old with 51 percent. Therefore, there are more 18 to 22 years old individuals who participated as respondents in the study. For highest educational attainment, 84 out of 158 respondents are college graduates with 53 percent, 57 out of 158 respondents are college undergraduate with 36 percent, 17 out of 158 respondents are undergraduate with 11 percent, while 17 out of 158 are high school graduates with 11 percent. Therefore, there are more college graduates who participated as respondents in the study.

Table 2. Mean Score for Poverty Factor

Demographic Profile	Variable	Mean Score	Verbal Interpretation	Description
Sex	Male	2.89	Agree	Respondents believe that poverty is a factor in increasing HIV cases
	Female	2.81	Agree	Respondents believe that poverty is a factor in increasing HIV cases
	Average	2.83	Agree	Respondents believe that poverty is a factor in increasing HIV cases
Age	33 and above	2.84	Agree	Respondents believe that poverty is a factor in increasing HIV cases
	28 to 32 years old	2.99	Agree	Respondents believe that poverty is a factor in increasing HIV cases
	23 to 27 years old	2.74	Agree	Respondents believe that poverty is a factor in increasing HIV cases
	18 to 22 years old	2.86	Agree	Respondents believe that poverty is a factor in increasing HIV cases
	Average	2.83	Agree	Respondents believe that poverty is a factor in increasing HIV cases
Highest Educational Attainment	College graduate	2.79	Agree	Respondents believe that poverty is a factor in increasing HIV cases
	College undergraduate	2.84	Agree	Respondents believe that poverty is a factor in increasing HIV cases
	High school graduate	3.03	Agree	Respondents believe that poverty is a factor in increasing HIV cases
	Average	2.83	Agree	Respondents believe that poverty is a factor in increasing HIV cases

The mean score of poverty per demographic profile is shown. For sex, male respondents obtained a mean score of 2.89 with verbal interpretation as “agree” while female respondents obtained a mean score of 2.81 with verbal interpretation as “agree”. Regardless of sex, respondents believed that poverty is a factor in increasing HIV cases. For age, respondents whose ages fall within 33 and above obtained a mean score of 2.84 with a verbal interpretation of “agree”, respondents whose ages fall within 28 to 32 obtained a mean score of 2.99 with a verbal interpretation of “agree”, respondents whose ages fall within 23 to 27 obtained a mean score of 2.74 with a verbal interpretation of “agree”, and respondents whose ages fall within 18 to 22 obtained a mean score of 2.26 with a verbal interpretation of “agree”. Across ages, respondents believed that poverty is a factor in increasing HIV cases. For highest educational attainment; college graduate respondents obtained a mean score of 2.79 with a verbal interpretation of “agree”; college undergraduate respondents obtained a mean score of 2.84 with a verbal interpretation of “agree”, and high school graduate respondents obtained a mean score of 3.03 with a verbal interpretation of “agree”. Across highest educational attainment, respondents believed that poverty is a factor in increasing HIV cases.

Table 3. Mean Score for Teenage Promiscuity Factor

Demographic Profile	Variable	Mean Score	Verbal Interpretation	Description
Sex	Male	2.97	Agree	Respondents believe that teenage promiscuity is a factor in increasing HIV cases
	Female	2.84	Agree	Respondents believe that teenage promiscuity is a factor in increasing HIV cases
	Average	2.87	Agree	Respondents believe that teenage promiscuity is a factor in increasing HIV cases
Age	33 and above	2.91	Agree	Respondents believe that teenage promiscuity is a factor in increasing HIV cases
	28 to 32 years old	3.09	Agree	Respondents believe that teenage promiscuity is a factor in increasing HIV cases
	23 to 27 years old	2.85	Agree	Respondents believe that teenage promiscuity is a factor in increasing HIV cases
	18 to 22 years old	2.85	Agree	Respondents believe that teenage promiscuity is a factor in increasing HIV cases
	Average	2.87	Agree	Respondents believe that teenage promiscuity is a factor in increasing HIV cases
Highest Educational Attainment	College graduate	2.93	Agree	Respondents believe that teenage promiscuity is a factor in increasing HIV cases
	College undergraduate	2.81	Agree	Respondents believe that teenage promiscuity is a factor in increasing HIV cases
	High school graduate	2.81	Agree	Respondents believe that teenage promiscuity is a factor in increasing HIV cases
	Average	2.87	Agree	Respondents believe that teenage promiscuity is a factor in increasing HIV cases

The mean score of teenage promiscuity per demographic profile is illustrated. For sex, male respondents obtained a mean score of 2.97 which was verbally interpreted as “agree” while female respondents obtained a mean score of 2.84 which was verbally interpreted as “agree”. Regardless of sex, respondents believed that teenage promiscuity is a factor in increasing HIV cases.

For age, respondents whose ages fall within 33 and above obtained a mean score of 2.91 with a verbal interpretation of “agree”, respondents whose ages fall within 28 to 32 obtained a mean score of 3.09 with a verbal interpretation of “agree”, respondents whose ages fall within 23 to 27 obtained a mean score of 2.85 with a verbal interpretation of “agree”, and respondents whose ages fall within 18 to 22 obtained a mean score of 2.85 with a verbal interpretation of “agree”. Across ages, respondents believed that teenage promiscuity is a factor in increasing HIV cases. For highest educational attainment, college graduate respondents obtained a mean score of 2.93 with a verbal interpretation of “agree”; college undergraduate respondents obtained a mean score of 2.81 with a verbal interpretation of “agree”, and high school graduate respondents obtained a

mean score of 2.81 with a verbal interpretation of “agree”. Across highest educational attainment, respondents believed that teenage promiscuity is a factor in increasing HIV cases.

Table 4. Mean Score for Substance Abuse Factor

Demographic Profile	Variable	Mean Score	Verbal Interpretation	Description
Sex	Male	2.87	Agree	Respondents believe that substance abuse is a factor in increasing HIV cases
	Female	2.75	Agree	Respondents believe that substance abuse is a factor in increasing HIV cases
	Average	2.78	Agree	Respondents believe that substance abuse is a factor in increasing HIV cases
Age	33 and above	2.91	Agree	Respondents believe that substance abuse is a factor in increasing HIV cases
	28 to 32 years old	3.11	Agree	Respondents believe that substance abuse is a factor in increasing HIV cases
	23 to 27 years old	2.73	Agree	Respondents believe that substance abuse is a factor in increasing HIV cases
	18 to 22 years old	2.73	Agree	Respondents believe that substance abuse is a factor in increasing HIV cases
	Average	2.78	Agree	Respondents believe that substance abuse is a factor in increasing HIV cases
Highest Educational Attainment	College graduate	2.81	Agree	Respondents believe that substance abuse is a factor in increasing HIV cases
	College undergraduate	2.67	Agree	Respondents believe that substance abuse is a factor in increasing HIV cases
	High school graduate	3.01	Agree	Respondents believe that substance abuse is a factor in increasing HIV cases
	Average	2.78	Agree	Respondents believe that substance abuse is a factor in increasing HIV cases

The mean score of substance abuse factor per demographic profile is presented. For sex, male respondents obtained a mean score of 2.87 which is verbally interpreted as “agree” while female respondents obtained a mean score of 2.75 which is verbally interpreted as “agree”. Regardless of sex, respondents believed that substance abuse is a factor in increasing HIV cases.

For age, respondents whose ages fall within 33 and above obtained a mean score of 2.91 with a verbal interpretation of “agree”, respondents whose ages fall within 28 to 32 obtained a mean score of 3.11 with a verbal interpretation of “agree”, respondents whose ages fall within 23 to 27 obtained a mean score of 2.73 with a verbal interpretation of “agree”, and respondents whose ages fall within 18 to 22 obtained a mean score of 2.73 with a verbal interpretation of agree. Across ages, respondents believed that substance abuse is a factor in increasing HIV cases. For highest educational attainment; college graduate respondents obtained a mean score of 2.81 with a verbal

interpretation of “agree”; college undergraduate respondents obtained a mean score of 2.67 with a verbal interpretation of “agree”, and high school graduate respondents obtained a mean score of 3.01 with a verbal interpretation of “agree”. Across highest educational attainment, respondents believed that substance abuse is a factor in increasing HIV cases.

Table 5. Mean Score for Family Relationship Factor

Demographic Profile	Variable	Mean Score	Verbal Interpretation	Description
Sex	Male	2.88	Agree	Respondents believe that misguidance in the family increases chances of HIV cases
	Female	2.86	Agree	Respondents believe that misguidance in the family increases chances of HIV cases
	Average	2.86	Agree	Respondents believe that misguidance in the family increases chances of HIV cases
Age	33 and above	2.95	Agree	Respondents believe that misguidance in the family increases chances of HIV cases
	28 to 32 years old	3.04	Agree	Respondents believe that misguidance in the family increases chances of HIV cases
	23 to 27 years old	2.82	Agree	Respondents believe that misguidance in the family increases chances of HIV cases
	18 to 22 years old	2.84	Agree	Respondents believe that misguidance in the family increases chances of HIV cases
	Average	2.86	Agree	Respondents believe that misguidance in the family increases chances of HIV cases
Highest Educational Attainment	College graduate	2.89	Agree	Respondents believe that misguidance in the family increases chances of HIV cases
	College undergraduate	2.82	Agree	Respondents believe that misguidance in the family increases chances of HIV cases
	High school graduate	2.89	Agree	Respondents believe that misguidance in the family increases chances of HIV cases
	Average	2.86	Agree	Respondents believe that misguidance in the family increases chances of HIV cases

The mean score of family relationship factor per demographic profile is shown. For sex, male respondents obtained a mean score of 2.88 which is verbally interpreted as “agree” while female respondents obtained a mean score of 2.86 which is verbally interpreted as “agree”. Regardless of sex, respondents believed that misguidance in the family increases chances of HIV cases.

For age, respondents whose ages fall within 33 and above obtained a mean score of 2.95 with a verbal interpretation of “agree”, respondents whose ages fall within 28 to 32 obtained a mean score of 3.04 with a verbal interpretation of “agree”, respondents whose ages fall within 23 to 27 obtained a mean score of 2.82 with a verbal interpretation of “agree”, and respondents whose

ages fall within 18 to 22 obtained a mean score of 2.84 with a verbal interpretation of “agree”. Across ages, respondents believed that misguidance in the family increases chances of HIV cases. For highest educational attainment; college graduate respondents obtained a mean score of 2.89 with a verbal interpretation of “agree”; college undergraduate respondents obtained a mean score of 2.82 with a verbal interpretation of agree, and high school graduate respondents obtained a mean score of 2.89 with a verbal interpretation of “agree”. Across highest educational attainment, respondents believed that misguidance in the family increases chances of HIV cases.

Table 6. Mean Score for Unsafe Sex Factor

Demographic Profile	Variable	Mean Score	Verbal Interpretation	Description
Sex	Male	2.93	Agree	Respondents believe that unsafe sex increases chances of HIV cases
	Female	2.97	Agree	Respondents believe that unsafe sex increases chances of HIV cases
	Average	2.96	Agree	Respondents believe that unsafe sex increases chances of HIV cases
Age	33 and above	2.94	Agree	Respondents believe that unsafe sex increases chances of HIV cases
	28 to 32 years old	3.19	Agree	Respondents believe that unsafe sex increases chances of HIV cases
	23 to 27 years old	2.95	Agree	Respondents believe that unsafe sex increases chances of HIV cases
	18 to 22 years old	2.93	Agree	Respondents believe that unsafe sex increases chances of HIV cases
	Average	2.96	Agree	Respondents believe that unsafe sex increases chances of HIV cases
Highest Educational Attainment	College graduate	3.00	Agree	Respondents believe that unsafe sex increases chances of HIV cases
	College undergraduate	2.89	Agree	Respondents believe that unsafe sex increases chances of HIV cases
	High school graduate	3.01	Agree	Respondents believe that unsafe sex increases chances of HIV cases
	Average	2.96	Agree	Respondents believe that unsafe sex increases chances of HIV cases

The table presents the average score of unsafe sex factor per demographic profile. For sex, male respondents received a mean score of 2.93, which was verbally perceived as “agree”, whereas female respondents received a mean score of 2.97, which was verbally interpreted as “agree”. Regardless of sex, the participants believed that unsafe sex increases the chances of HIV cases. For age, respondents whose ages fall within 33 and above obtained a mean score of 2.94 with a verbal interpretation of “agree”, respondents whose ages fall within 28 to 32 acquired a mean score of 3.19 with a verbal interpretation of “agree”, respondents whose ages fall within 23

to 27 obtained a mean score of 2.95 with a verbal interpretation of “agree”, and respondents whose ages fall within 18 to 22 obtained a mean score of 2.93 with a verbal interpretation of “agree”. Across ages, respondents believed that unsafe sex increases the chances of HIV cases. For highest educational attainment; college graduate respondents obtained a mean score of 3.00 with a verbal interpretation of “agree”; college undergraduate respondents obtained a mean score of 2.89 with a verbal interpretation of “agree”, and high school graduate respondents obtained a mean score of 3.01 with a verbal interpretation of “agree”. Across highest educational attainment, respondents believed that unsafe sex increases the chances of HIV cases.

Table 7. Test for Significant Difference for Sex

Factor	p-value	Significance	H₀ Decision
Poverty	0.46	Not Significant	Accept
Teenage Promiscuity	0.15	Not Significant	Accept
Substance Abuse	0.29	Not Significant	Accept
Family Relationship	0.86	Not Significant	Accept
Unsafe Sex	0.77	Not Significant	Accept

**Significant at .05 alpha level*

The test for significant difference across all factors for sex demographic profile is illustrated. For Poverty factor, the computed p-value is 0.46 which is greater than .05 alpha level. Hence, the difference between male and female mean score is not significant and the null hypothesis is rejected. Therefore, regardless of sex, they felt at the same level of agreement that poverty is a factor in increasing HIV cases.

Few studies favor the view that in some other countries there is an increase in HIV cases as a level of wealth rather than poverty (Mishra et al., 2014). Data on national surveys of eight sub-Saharan countries indicate that levels of HIV positive increase as wealth rises. Analyzing demographic survey data for Kenya in 2003, Johnson and Way (2006) show that HIV has a positive correlation with wealth for both men and women (with the richest women being 2.6 times more likely to be HIV-positive than the poorest). Bärnighausen et al. (2007) shows in another large-scale longitudinal data series in South Africa that middle-level wealth is linked with an increased incidence of seroconversion to HIV. However, it may be difficult to decide whether an individual is positive or not, based on wealth.

For the factor of teenage promiscuity, the p-value measured is 0.15 which is higher than the alpha level of .05. The discrepancy between male and female mean is therefore not important, and the null hypothesis is rejected. Consequently, regardless of sex, at the same level of agreement they felt that promiscuity among adolescents is a factor that contributes to the increase of HIV cases. The estimated p-value for Substance abuse factor is 0.29, which is higher than the alpha level of .05. The discrepancy between male and female mean scores is therefore not important, and the null hypothesis is rejected. They also felt at the same degree of agreement, regardless of age, that drug abuse is a factor that contributes to the increase of HIV cases.

For Family Relationship factor, the computed p-value is 0.86 which is greater than .05 alpha level. Hence, the difference between male and female mean score is not significant and the

null hypothesis is rejected. Therefore, regardless of sex, they felt at the same level of agreement that misguidance in the family increases chances of HIV cases.

For Unsafe Sex factor, the computed p-value is 0.77 which is greater than .05 alpha level. Hence, the difference between male and female mean score is not significant and the null hypothesis is rejected. Therefore, regardless of sex, they felt at the same level of agreement that unsafe sex increases the chances of HIV cases.

Table 8. Test for Significant Difference for Age

Factor	p-value	Significance	H₀ Decision
Poverty	0.38	Not Significant	Accept
Teenage Promiscuity	0.42	Not Significant	Accept
Substance Abuse	0.12	Not Significant	Accept
Family Relationship	0.53	Not Significant	Accept
Unsafe Sex	0.54	Not Significant	Accept

**Significant at .05 alpha level*

The test for significant difference across all factors for age demographic profile is presented. The p-value calculated for the poverty factor is 0.38. It is a much more significant amount than .05. Hence, the difference among age bracket mean scores is not significant and the null hypothesis is rejected. Therefore, regardless of age, they felt at the same level of agreement that poverty is a factor in increasing HIV cases. The calculated p-value for Teenage Promiscuity factor is 0.42 which is a more significant value than .05. Hence, the difference among age bracket mean scores is not significant and the null hypothesis is rejected. Therefore, regardless of age, they felt at the same level of agreement that teenage promiscuity is a factor in increasing HIV cases. The calculated p-value for Substance Abuse factor is 0.12. This value is more significant than .05. Hence, the difference among age bracket mean scores is not significant and the null hypothesis is rejected. Therefore, regardless of age, substance abuse contributes largely in the increasing number cases of HIV. The calculated p-value for the Family Relationship factor is 0.53, a much more significant value than .05. Hence, the difference among age bracket mean scores is not significant and the null hypothesis is rejected. Therefore, regardless of age, they felt at the same level of agreement that misguidance in the family increases chances of HIV cases. The calculated p-value for the Unsafe Sex factor is 0.54. This is of greater value than .05. Hence, the difference among age bracket mean scores is not significant and the null hypothesis is rejected.

Therefore, regardless of age, they felt at the same level of agreement that unsafe sex increases the chances of HIV cases. In relationships, it is important to have knowledge on your partner's sexual history to have a safe and healthy sexual life. It is better to consult a medical professional and take a test before.

Table 9. Test for Significant Difference for Highest Educational Attainment

Factor	p-value	Significance	H₀ Decision
Poverty	0.24	Not Significant	Accept
Teenage Promiscuity	0.35	Not Significant	Accept
Substance Abuse	0.09	Not Significant	Accept
Family Relationship	0.77	Not Significant	Accept
Unsafe Sex	0.57	Not Significant	Accept

**Significant at .05 alpha level*

The above table shows the test for significant difference across all factors for highest educational attainment demographic profile. The calculated p-value for Poverty factor is 0.24, a much more significant value than .05. Hence, the difference among highest educational attainment mean scores is not significant and the null hypothesis is rejected. Therefore, regardless of highest educational attainment, they felt at the same level of agreement that poverty is a factor in increasing HIV cases. The calculated p-value for Teenage Promiscuity factor is 0.35. This is a more significant value than .05. Hence, the difference among highest educational attainment mean scores is not significant and the null hypothesis is rejected. Therefore, regardless of highest educational attainment, they felt at the same level of agreement that teenage promiscuity is a factor in increasing HIV cases. The calculated p-value is 0.09 for Substance Abuse Factor. This is more significant than .05. Hence, the difference among highest educational attainment mean scores is not significant and the null hypothesis is rejected. Therefore, regardless of highest educational attainment, they felt at the same level of agreement that substance abuse is a factor in increasing HIV cases. The calculated p-value for Family Relationship factor is 0.77, a more significant value than .05. Hence, the difference among highest educational attainment mean scores is not significant and the null hypothesis is rejected. Therefore, regardless of highest educational attainment, they felt at the same level of agreement that misguidance in the family increases chances of HIV cases. The calculated p-value for Unsafe Sex factor is 0.57. This is a more significant value than .05. Hence, the difference among highest educational attainment mean scores is not significant and the null hypothesis is rejected. Therefore, regardless of highest educational attainment, they felt at the same level of agreement that unsafe sex increases the chances of HIV cases.

Discussion

According to Amuri et al. (2012), sex was another factor of PLHIV discrimination. It is also demonstrated that women are more aware than men of HIV in the society (Ouzouni & Nakakis, 2012). Nevertheless, in comparison to previous research, the findings of this study found that women have more pessimistic and misinformed opinions towards PLHIV compared to men in terms of poverty (Ipsos MORI, 2011).

Discrimination towards people living with HIV has been widely reported in Hong Kong, yet a substantial level of discriminatory attitudes towards PLWHA has been documented among adults, adolescents, social workers, health services providers, and people in the workplace. According to Lau and Tsui (2005), people in China ages 18 to 50 years that were randomly selected, 42% of the respondents were shown discrimination among people living with HIV.

However, the increase of poverty in Sahara Africa shows the usage of condoms by young people and teenagers remains relatively low. Demographic and Health Surveys conducted in sub-Saharan Africa between 2010 and 2015 show that fewer than 60 per cent of young women (aged 15 to 24) with multiple partners used contraceptives during their last sexual encounter in 19 of 23 nations. Similar results for young men have been observed in 15 out of 23 countries (Prevention Gap Report, UNAIDS, 2016).

Poor social popularity has been believed to increase the chance of HIV infection through its associated factors, such as low schooling, which reduce the likelihood of obtaining the expertise needed to adopt more secure sexual behaviors (Nubed & Akoachere, 2016). In addition, the effects showed that, despite of comparable rates of employment, the vulnerable were far less likely to have accurate knowledge about an effective means of avoiding HIV infection. Studies no longer offer explanations for this and, as such, more experiments are needed to define the factors (Nubed & Akoachere, 2016).

According to Collins (2011), in the US teenagers are a major public health concern. Almost 800,000 young women between 15 and 19 years of age become infertile every year in the United States, most of them unintentionally. Women's low turnout could be due to low status and restrictions imposed on women by backward societies, making them ignorant of sexually acquired diseases such as HIV. In terms of HIV positivity, the proportion of males was higher than those of females. Also, males who test positive rarely disclose their HIV status to their partners or spouses, making females oblivious to transmission. Males who test positive rarely disclose their HIV status to their partners or spouses, making females oblivious to the risk of transmission (Kurapati et al., 2012).

A vast section of the global population, over 1.75 billion, is young and aged between 10 and 24 years, making every fifth person on earth a teenager. Due to the transitional nature of the whole age category, they are susceptible to HIV / AIDS. According to Kurapati et al. (2012), around the world adolescent is the fifth person in the world ages between 10 to 24 years old. Despite of this large scale of population, they are vulnerable to HIV / AIDS. In addition, other factors such as lack of HIV / AIDS knowledge, inaccessibility to healthcare services and commodities, lack of education and life skills, and early marriage have increased their vulnerability to HIV / AIDS. As adolescents are a major part of the reproductive group, they are likely to play a significant role in determining the future pattern of growth of India's population and economy. It is also important that innovation in infrastructure, science and technology strategies is made to enhance their well-being.

Young people of their generation should learn how to use condoms properly and that they should be willing to address condom usage with their friends in an impartial way (Jones et al., 2013). However, before adolescents can discuss the use of condoms among themselves, they need accurate information from a reliable source. Parents, guardians, and teachers are in an ideal position to teach their student or child about sex education therefore some of the school and parents are not comfortable talking to this kind of issue. That why parents should educate their children the responsible of using condoms and contraceptives, so they may know the correct information regarding to the myths and misconception towards HIV (Jones et al., 2013).

The rise of HIV infections in Puerto Rico may prove to be an example to this data. One of the foremost causes of transmitting the virus among Hispanics is by means of Injection Drug Use (IDU) (CDC, 2008). Furthermore, using drugs during intercourse is often found too common

among both Hispanic men and Hispanic women, with roughly 25% of the community stating that they indeed drink alcohol frequently while engaging into intercourse (González-Guarda et al., 2011; Zellner et al., 2009). Hispanic MSM's who perform anal intercourse without protection most often think that alcohol consumption gives an intense sexual desire and masks vulnerability (Balan et al., 2009).

For the data discussed above, a comparison between the number of HIV/AIDS cases among Hispanic women proved to be seven times more than that of white women (CDC, 2008). Yet, among people aged 25 years old to 44 years old, HIV/AIDS has been the leading fatality which leads to death in the United States of America (CDC, 2008). Nonetheless, approximately 47 percent of Hispanic women living with HIV acquired the disease by having intercourse with partners who are not aware, that they too, are infected. Most of the women contracted the virus through IDU or through having intercourse who are IDU's, clearly and entirely oblivious to the risks (Celentano et al., 2008).

Having the means to take care of a person's health behavior may come from different, specific knowledge. By saying that, people with little to no education at all could have less resources to take their own health behavior into their own hands. For example, females that are at an advantage because they were able to attend institutions for higher learning have been described to have a stronger self-esteem rather than those who have less education. High self-esteem gives females a sense of self-worth, making this as an important motivation for their sexual health (Abel & Chambers, 2004).

Participation by men regarding comprehensive family planning is often nonexistent in today's society. In India, for example promotion of family planning and clarifying information towards conception is not really a priority (Raj et al., 2016). A study in Kathmandu Valley showed that almost 75% of males who were aware that they are HIV positive still engaged in sexual relations in the past six months, and only about 46% used protection. This notion is very dangerous because HIV is a communicable form of disease.

The misconceptions about the relevance of contraceptives for PLHIV's exist in modern day society simply because there are side effects that could potentially happen. At present, a lot of women who wants to remain carefree by avoiding pregnancy do not use modern contraceptive methods. This is mainly because of the raising concerns towards the risks of these women taking contraceptives. This raises a problem in modern society because as the population increases, so does the number of HIV cases. Use of the contraceptive method along with males using condoms as they engage into sexual relations play a significant role in the increase of HIV transmissions (Parks, 2019)

In a study done in Africa, it was shown that educational attainment plays a massive role in being a predictor of testing for HIV among women, especially in women mature enough to bear children. Women who did not reach college education were almost not fully aware about the testing benefits for HIV. The higher education one has attained, the more open-minded a person can be. It is crucial that education about sexually transmitted diseases be accessible to children, teenagers, and sexually active individuals (Muyunda et al., 2018).

Latest studies have shown that a large number of HIV-positive individuals participate in high-risk sexual activities. Although many people living with HIV / AIDS either refrain from sex or substantially reduce risky sexual activity, a large percentage of HIV-positive people (from 10%

to 64 percent) tend to engage in risky sexual activity. A deeper understanding of the underlying mechanisms and associations of these high-risk sexual activities among people living with HIV / AIDS remains a concern for researchers and public health practitioners alike (Li et al., 2012).

High-risk sexual activity and the risk of HIV infection are especially high among people who use drugs. Apart from the obvious risk of HIV infection from needle sharing, some studies have identified high-risk sexual activity among HIV positive injection drug users (IDUs) as a major association (Li et al., 2012). The prevalence of HIV / AIDS among adults 49 and older is on the increase due, in part, to risky sexual activities frequently induced by drug abuse. Weak negotiation skills, sensational quest, exchange of sex for money or drugs, negative perceptions of outcomes (i.e. loss of privacy, stigma, rejection of sex), multiple sex partners, and safer sex exhaustion (resulting from long-term exposure to prevention messages and too many years of secure sex) have also been related to risky sexual behavior among HIV-positive people (Li et al., 2012).

Studies of stigmatizing attitudes of the general population toward PLHIV indicate that HIV/AIDS-based stigma is inversely linked to awareness of HIV transmission patterns, educational attainment, and possibly, it is related to the age. The present research also found that bisexual MSM was inversely correlated with HIV testing. A study among MSM in Shandong found that bisexual men are more likely to be older and have lower levels of HIV-related knowledge than men who have sex with men alone. The bisexual activities identified in this study are consistent with earlier studies and other reports in China and are more widespread than those documented in the West. Chinese culture is still relatively cautious when it comes to discussing homosexuality as an open topic (Li et al., 2012).

Clinical and behavioral reviews and clinical findings have related victimization of the childhood to a number of negative health and behavioral consequences. According to Widom and Kuhns (1996), based on their findings that childhood victimization is not a major risk factor for promiscuity or teenage pregnancy, the general perception that childhood victimization is correlated with adolescent promiscuity and teenage pregnancy. That is, they found no significant association between abuse / neglect of early childhood and promiscuity and adolescent pregnancy, either in bivariate or in multivariate analyzes that monitored age, race sex, and child welfare status. The findings are therefore not in line with general standards or prior studies on these two outcomes. This study, however, differs from most past research in the forward-looking nature of design and the inclusion of a control group. The prospective design of this research allows for the examination of certain causality problems and disentangles the effect of childhood victimization from other possible conflicting impacts.

The findings of this study support the concept of family centrality in Thai culture and the importance of family support to PLHIV. Such results and the clear cultural expectations for families existing in Thailand indicate that care should be reorganized in order to provide more family-based services (Knodel & Im-em, 2004). Our family functioning measure included several indices: an overview of the quality and sound of everyday interactions within the family; and indices of cohesiveness, problem solving, and family conflict. Families with an organized and structured family life in the United States have a better quality of life (Weisner, 2008; Weisner et al., 2002; Weisner & Lowe, 2004). Physical and mental health indexes benefit from consistent daily routines that are positive in tone, high cohesiveness, problem solving, and family relationships that are low in conflict. Strong, consistent routines are also likely to help families

keep order and balance in the face of devastating illness. HIV requires such adaptation and is likely to tax the ability of the entire family to cope with the disease.

The existing research simulates previous studies to show that the cluster of poverty indicators is closely related to poor health outcomes for people living with HIV (Leaver et al., 2007; Tsai et al., 2012). In our research, there has been a strong and independent correlation between several food insecurity markers and HIV suppression markers. Individuals with unfettered HIV were more than twice as likely to have unsafe housing and more than twice as likely to have inadequate transportation to health care and food sources.

With these basic knowledge, stigma and discrimination toward people living with HIV will be lessen or best if eradicated. Stigma is a hindrance in eliminating the spread of HIV. People with HIV cannot come out of their boxes if people continuously discriminate against them. This way, the researchers together with the Bacoor community might be able to completely eradicate not only the stigma, but also the spread of HIV.

More participants decrease the possibility of an unreliable research since it covers more ground for investigative analysis. Therefore, the study must have additional participants with a broader range of demographics. Since the study is attempting to determine psychosocial perceptions of non-HIV individuals, an admixture of both Quantitative and Qualitative research methodology might be best to gain more insights on the behaviors of the participants. Seeing as stigmatized beliefs are the foremost instigators of disparities between healthy individuals and the HIV positive community, empathizing with the latter and understanding things from their point of view by means of a thorough yet comprehensive interview is essential.

References

- Abel, E., & Chambers, K. (2004). Factors that influence vulnerability to STDs and HIV/AIDS among Hispanic women. *Health Care for Women International*, 25(8), 761-780. <https://doi.org/10.1080/07399330490475601>
- Amuri, M., Mitchell, S., Cockcroft, A., & Andersson, N. (2011). Socio-economic status and HIV/AIDS stigma in Tanzania. *AIDS Care*, 23(3), 378-382. <https://doi.org/10.1080/09540121.2010.507739>
- Bärnighausen, T., Hosegood, V., Timaeus, I. M., & Newell, M. L. (2007). The socioeconomic determinants of HIV incidence: evidence from a longitudinal, population-based study in rural South Africa. *AIDS*, 21(Suppl 7), S29-S38.
- Celentano, D. D., Latimore, A. D., & Mehta, S. H. (2008). Variations in sexual risks in drug users: emerging themes in a behavioral context. *Current HIV/AIDS Reports*, 5(4), 212-218. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11904-008-0030-4>
- Centers for Disease Control and Prevention. (2008). *Estimated rates of diagnoses of HIV infection among adults and adolescents, by sex and race/ethnicity, 2008—37 states with confidential name-based HIV infection reporting*. HIV Surveillance Report (vol. 20). https://www.cdc.gov/hiv/pdf/statistics_2008_HIV_Surveillance_Report_vol_20.pdf
- González-Guarda, R. M., McCabe, B. E., Florom-Smith, A., Cianelli, R., & Peragallo, N. (2011). Substance abuse, violence, HIV, and depression. *Nursing Research*, 60(3), 182-189. <https://doi.org/10.1097/nnr.0b013e318216d5f4>

- Ipsos MORI. (2011, February 18). *Public attitudes towards HIV*. <https://www.ipsos.com/ipsos-mori/en-uk/public-attitudes-towards-hiv-1>
- Johnson, K., & Way, A. (2006). Risk factors for HIV infection in a national adult population: Evidence from the 2003 Kenya Demographic and Health Survey. *JAIDS Journal of Acquired Immune Deficiency Syndromes*, 42(5), 627-636. <https://doi.org/10.1097/01.qai.0000225870.87456.ae>
- Joint United Nations Programme on HIV/AIDS. (2018, August 14). *Cities in Philippines pledge to lower HIV infections and improve their track record*. <https://www.unaids.org/en/resources/presscentre/featurestories/2018/august/philippines>
- Joint United Nations Programme on HIV/AIDS. (2019). *Country progress report - Philippines*. https://www.unaids.org/sites/default/files/country/documents/PHL_2019_countryreport.pdf
- Jones, V., Modeste, N., Marshak, H. H., & Fox, C. (2013). The effect of HIV/AIDS education on adolescents in Trinidad and Tobago. *International Scholarly Research Notices*, 2013, 691054. <https://doi.org/10.5402/2013/691054>
- Knodel, J., & Im-Em, W. (2004). The economic consequences for parents of losing an adult child to AIDS: Evidence from Thailand. *Social Science & Medicine*, 59(5), 987-1001. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.socscimed.2003.11.042>
- Kurapati, S., Vajpayee, M., Raina, M., & Vishnubhatla, S. (2012). Adolescents living with HIV: An Indian profile. *AIDS Research and Treatment*, 2012, 576149. <https://doi.org/10.1155/2012/576149>
- Lau, J. T. F., & Tsui, H. Y. (2005). Discriminatory attitudes towards people living with HIV/AIDS and associated factors: A population based study in the Chinese general population. *Sexually Transmitted Infections*, 81(2), 113-119. <https://doi.org/10.1136/sti.2004.011767>
- Leaver, C. A., Bargh, G., Dunn, J. R., & Hwang, S. W. (2007). The effects of housing status on health-related outcomes in people living with HIV: a systematic review of the literature. *AIDS and Behavior*, 11(2), 85-100. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10461-007-9246-3>
- Li, X., Lu, H., Ma, X., Sun, Y., He, X., Li, C., Raymond, H. F., McFarland, W., Pan, S. W., Shao, Y., Vermund, S. H., Xiao, Y., Ruan, Y., & Jia, Y. (2012). HIV/AIDS-related stigmatizing and discriminatory attitudes and recent HIV testing among men who have sex with men in Beijing. *AIDS and Behavior*, 16(3), 499-507. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10461-012-0161-x>
- Mishra, S. R., Joshi, M. P., & Khanal, V. (2014). Family planning knowledge and practice among people living with HIV in Nepal. *PLoS ONE*, 9(2), e88663. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0088663>
- Muyunda, B., Musonda, P., Mee, P., Todd, J., & Michelo, C. (2018). Educational attainment as a predictor of HIV testing uptake among women of child-bearing age: analysis of 2014 demographic and health survey in Zambia. *Frontiers in Public Health*, 6, 192. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fpubh.2018.00192>
- Nubed, C. K., & Akoachere, J. F. T. K. (2016). Knowledge, attitudes and practices regarding HIV/AIDS among senior secondary school students in Fako Division, South West Region, Cameroon. *BMC Public Health*, 16, 847. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12889-016-3516-9>
- Nworgu, B. G. (1991). *Educational research: Basic issues and methodology*. Wisdom Publishers Ltd.
- Ouzouni, C., & Nakakis, K. (2012). HIV/AIDS knowledge, attitudes and behaviours of student nurses. *Health Science Journal*, 6(1), 129-150.

- Parks, J. (2019, January 24). *Myths, misconceptions still discourage use of family planning*. Population Reference Bureau. <https://www.prb.org/resources/myths-misconceptions-still-discourage-use-of-family-planning/>
- QuestionPro. (n.d.). *Quantitative research: Definition, methods, types and examples*. <https://www.questionpro.com/blog/quantitative-research/>
- Raj, A., Ghule, M., Ritter, J., Battala, M., Gajanan, V., Nair, S., Dasgupta, A., Silverman, J. G., Balaiah, D., & Saggurti, N. (2016). Cluster randomized controlled trial evaluation of a gender equity and family planning intervention for married men and couples in rural India. *PLoS ONE*, *11*(5), e0153190.
- Tanggol, F. (2019, January 11). *New law important boost to HIV response in the Philippines*. World Health Organization. <https://www.who.int/philippines/news/detail/11-01-2019-new-law-important-boost-to-hiv-response-in-the-philippines>
- Tsai, A. C., Bangsberg, D. R., Frongillo, E. A., Hunt, P. W., Muzoora, C., Martin, J. N., & Weiser, S. D. (2012). Food insecurity, depression and the modifying role of social support among people living with HIV/AIDS in rural Uganda. *Social Science & Medicine*, *74*(12). <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.socscimed.2012.02.033>
- Weisner, T. (2008). Understanding new hope: A successful antipoverty program for working poor adults and their children. *Anthropology News*, *49*(4), 19-20. http://www.tweisner.com/yahoo_site_admin/assets/docs/Weisner_20086_Understanding_New_Hope_Newsletter_F48.231162245.pdf
- Weisner, T. S., Gibson, C., Lowe, E. D., & Romich, J. (2002). Understanding working poor families in the New Hope Program. *Poverty Research Newsletter*, *6*(4), 3-5.
- Weisner, T. S. & Lowe, E. (2004). Globalization and the psychological anthropology of childhood and adolescence. In C. Casey & R. Edgerton (Eds.), *A companion to psychological anthropology: Modernity and psychocultural change* (pp. 318–336). Blackwell.
- Widom, C. S., & Kuhns, J. B. (1996). Childhood victimization and subsequent risk for promiscuity, prostitution, and teenage pregnancy: a prospective study. *American Journal of Public Health*, *86*(11), 1607-1612. <https://doi.org/10.2105/AJPH.86.11.1607>
- Zellner, J. A., Martínez-Donate, A. P., Sañudo, F., Fernández-Cerdeño, A., Sipan, C. L., Hovell, M. F., & Carrillo, H. (2009). The interaction of sexual identity with sexual behavior and its influence on HIV risk among Latino men: Results of a community survey in northern San Diego County, California. *American Journal of Public Health*, *99*(1), 125-132. <https://doi.org/10.2105/AJPH.2007.129809>